

THE EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF COMPOSITE PROTON EXCHANGE MEMBRANE

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This paper investigates the thermal properties of composite membrane produced by Wuhan WUT New Energy Co., Ltd. (WUT). The thermal conductivities of 6 kinds of domestic proton exchange membranes with different thickness are measured. The result shows that the thermal conductivity of composite membrane does not vary with the thickness and the maximum deviation is 3.5%.

1. Introduction

Proton exchange membrane (PEM) is one of the most important core components of proton exchange membrane fuel cell [1]. It is different from the membrane in the normal chemical power. This membrane has three functions: transferring protons, separating reaction gases, preventing passage of free electrons [2]. The material used to produce PEM must have good proton conductivity. Moreover, the permeation of water molecules and gas should be less. It also needs a good electrochemical stability, a certain mechanical strength, a better conversion property under dry and wet atmosphere, and reasonable price.

In 1890, Ostwald studied the characters of semipermeable membrane, finding that the membrane was impermeable to any electrolyte if it is impermeable to anions or cations [3]. Michaelis and Fujita studied the ion exchange membrane in detail and invented weak acid collodion membrane in 1925 [4]. Ion exchange membrane was still in the laboratory stage of development until 1950. Juda and McRac [5] in 1950 and Winger et al [6] in 1953 both had contributed to the stability and selectivity of ion exchange membrane and promoted its industrialization application. In 1970s, Dupont Corporation invented Nafion, a kind of perfluorinated sulfonic membrane. This kind of PEM has good electrical conductivity and long service life for 104-105 hours [7]. Nafion membrane is still studied as a standard membrane used in proton exchange membrane fuel cells. Meanwhile, in 1976, Chlanda developed a bipolar composite membrane with a cation exchange layer and anion exchange layer [8], bringing lots of new development for the application of electrodialysis [9]. Actually, the research on ion exchange membrane not only focused on polymer. By using silicate, phosphate and other inorganic materials, we can get high temperature resistance membranes, but these membranes have drawbacks of high cost, bad electrochemical properties and large aperture [1], so these membranes are not widely concerned and used.

In order to obtain the ion exchange membrane with good chemical stability and high conductivity, at the end of 1990s, organic and inorganic ion exchange membranes were successfully applied in higher temperature and strong oxidizing environment. DuPont Co Nafion produced by DuPont, Gore-Select produced by Gore, PFSA produced by 3M Corporation, Acplex produced by Asahi Kasei and Flemion produced by Asahi glass, AquivionTM produced by a Belgian company named Solvay, and Dongyue Membrane produced by Shandong Dongyue

Group production of Chinese film, these membrane above are all fully fluorinated membranes. New Energy Company of Wuhan University of Technology developed a composite membranes formed by the combination of perfluorinated sulfonic acid resin and PTFE porous membrane, which can still have good mechanical strength and stability when it is very thin, so it is a new type of composite membrane with potential commercialization [1].

From the article [10,11], both the temperature and water content of the membrane have a great influence on the properties of the PEM. But most researchers are focusing on how to design a new type of PEM, improve the electrical conductivity of PEM and design a thin PEM with good mechanical properties. It is far from enough to stay in the above research when the trends in the commercialization of fuel cells are coming. Therefore, the focus of the research is gradually extended to all aspects of the whole fuel cell system, especially the development of water management and thermal management system of fuel cell system. This is necessary for the commercialization of fuel cells. So the thermal conductivity of proton exchange membrane (PEMFC) is measured by experiment.

2. Experimental principle

Based on hot wire method, Transient Plane Source technology has become an ISO standard [12] for thermal conductivity measurement. As shown in Figure 1, a thin layer of disk shaped resistance wire is used as the sample probe, and the cover of probe with a double helix structure is formed by the polyimide or mica insulating layer. When testing, the probe must be placed between two pieces of the same sample to form a sandwich structure, as shown in Figure 2. In this paper, the two samples are homogeneous. And the flat sensor consists of double spiral of resistance wire made of nickel metal, etched out of a thin foil. The nickel spiral is situated between two layers of thin polyimide or mica sheet, as shown in Figure 1, and the cladding of the spiral provides electrical insulation and mechanical stability to the sensor. The samples to be tested should be thick and big enough to ensure that the heat generation wouldn't transport to the edge, in order to satisfy the semi-infinite assumption.

Figure 1 Kapton 7280 sensor for measuring heat conductivity

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of test fixture

The Hot Disk method assumes that there are numbers of concentric heat source inside the infinite samples, and on the one hand, the double spiral sensor works as a heat source, on the other hand, as a temperature sensor. When the Hot Disk is electrically heated, the sensor is electrically heated, and its resistance will change with time as the Formula (1):

$$R(t) = R_0(1 + \alpha\Delta T) = R_0[1 + \alpha\Delta T_i + \alpha\Delta T_{ins}(\tau)] \quad (1)$$

where t is testing time, whose unit is s ; R_0 is resistance of sensor before heating when $t=0$, whose unit is Ω ; α is temperature coefficient of resistance, whose unit is K^{-1} ; τ is dimensionless time, $\tau = \sqrt{t/\Xi}$, here, $\Xi = r^2/a$, r is the radius (mm) of the sensor and a is thermal diffusivity (mm^2/s) of the background material; ΔT is the average temperature rise, whose unit is K ; ΔT_i is temperature difference between two sides of the sensor, whose unit is K ; ΔT_{ins} is the temperature rise of the surface facing the sensor of background material, whose unit is K .

From the Formula (1), temperature increment taken by sensor can be written as:

$$\Delta T_i + \Delta T_{ins} = (R(t)/R_0 - 1)/\alpha \quad (2)$$

where ΔT_i is temperature difference between sensor and sample surface, when its value is 0, it shows that the ideal thermal contact is realized. ΔT_i will become a constant after the time of Δt_i , because the sample is very thin and the power is invariable. Normally, Δt_i can be estimated by:

$$\Delta t_i = \delta^2/\lambda_i \quad (3)$$

where δ is the thickness of the insulating layer; λ_i is the thermal diffusivity of the insulating layer.

Due to the assumption that the probe sensor is made up of a series of concentric circular heat

sources, the time-based temperature rise is shown in the Formula (4):

$$\Delta T_{ins}(\tau) = \frac{P_0}{\pi^{3/2} r \lambda} E(\tau) \quad (4)$$

where P_0 is total output power of sensor, whose unit is W ; λ is heat conductivity of sample, whose unit is $W/(mK)$.

In Formula (4), $E(\tau)$ is a time-based function which has nothing to do with size, and its concrete expression is:

$$E(\tau) = [m(m+1)]^{-2} \int_0^\tau \sigma^{-2} \left[\sum_{l=1}^m l \sum_{k=1}^m k \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-(l^2+k^2)}{4m^2\sigma^2}\right) I_0\left(\frac{lk}{2m^2\sigma^2}\right) \right] \left[1 + 2 \sum_{i=1}^\infty \exp\left(-\frac{i^2 h^2}{\sigma^2 \tau^2}\right) \right] d\sigma \quad (5)$$

where I_0 is modified Bessel function; m is number of concentric circular heat sources; h is thickness of probe sensor.

Make: $R^* = R_0(1 + \alpha \Delta T_i)$, $C = \alpha R_0 P_0 / \pi^{3/2} r \lambda$. Take Formula (4) into Formula (1) and then we can get:

$$R(t) = R^* + CE(\tau) \quad (6)$$

Due to ΔT_i will become a constant in a very short time, R^* will become a constant soon. And absolutely, C is a constant. So $R(t)$ depends on $E(\tau)$ linearly. $E(\tau)$ can be calculated by the testing temperature rise. On the basis of above, we can get Formula (6) and the fitting curve by least square method.

The Hot Disk method assumes that there are certain quantities of concentric heat sources in the infinite sample. The double helix structure sensor is used as heat source on the one hand, and on the other hand as the temperature sensor. While the Hot Disk is ohmic heating, the sensor will be heated by electricity, and the formula (1) shows the law that resistance change as time.

3. Experimental preparation

Table 1 types of sample

Samples	DCM1	DCM2	DCM3	DCM4	DCM5	DCM6
Thickness/ μm	15	40	65	90	115	140

In this experiment, the samples are bought from Wuhan WUT New Energy Co., Ltd, which is a kind of composite proton exchange membrane used PFSA that strengthened by ePTFE, hereinafter referred to as domestic composite membrane. Table 1 shows the samples offered by different manufacturers. The thickness is used to distinguish the types of membrane. There are total 6 kinds of membranes, and each test needs two pieces.

Quanta 250 FEG environmental scanning electron microscope. The floccules are caused by cutting, and it is clear that a plenty of voids on the membrane, which offer a space for water molecules.

In order to reduce the effect of evaporation, a low temperature and a high humidity

environment is necessary to reduce evaporation. The time of PEM soaking in the ultrapure water is controlled. After soaking for a period of time, we removed it out and wiped off the surface water quickly. In order to ensure the accuracy of measurement, we use high precision electronic balance to get its weight for more than three times and choose the average value as the measured value. Table 2 shows the relationship between water content and time.

From Table 2, it can be seen that the water content doesn't vary obviously with the increment of the immersed time. The water content of DCM1 is evidently higher than the other, whose reason may be the DCM1 is too thin to wipe the water on its surface absolutely. Ignoring the DCM1, we can find that the water content of different thickness DCM is not very different.

4. Result and discussion

As function of PEM in proton exchange membrane fuel cell, there is a lot of researches focused on its thermal conductivity. However, taking various the small structures of samples, the preparation method, experimental testing method, the apparent thermal conductivity and the essence thermal conductivity into condition, there are great differences among the result offered by many references. Except the thermal conductivity, the change trend of thermal conductivity is different. This paper measures the thermal conductivity among dry state composite membranes with different thicknesses and composite membranes with different water content.

In this paper, the heat conductivity of dry DCM is measured at ambient temperature and pressure, and the result is shown as Table 2. Except for DCM1, the heat conductivity of membrane is not significantly affected by its thickness and the maximum deviation is 3.5%. The DCM1 is too thin to accurately measure.

Table 2 Heat conductivities of DCM with different thickness

PEM thickness/ μm	15	50	62	95	115	160
Heat conductivity/ $\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	0.0161	0.0615	0.0664	0.0661	0.06846	0.06617

Table 2 shows the thermal conductivity of dry state membranes with different thicknesses under normal temperature and pressure. We find that, except the PEM with thickness of $15\mu\text{m}$, membrane's thermal conductivity is basically unaffected by thicknesses, and the maximum deviation is 3.5%. The experimental error of DCM1 may be caused by thickness.

5. Conclusion

This paper investigates the thermal properties of composite membrane produced by Wuhan University of Technology New Energy Company. The thermal conductivities of 6 kinds of domestic proton exchange membranes with different thickness are measured. The result shows that the thermal conductivity of PEM does not vary with the thickness and the maximum deviation is 3.5%, except for DCM with the thickness of $15\mu\text{m}$. DCM1 may be too thin, resulting in a large error in the experimental measurement.

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